

Danang Technovation

Impact Enterprise

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Forbes Vietnam 30 Under 30 –2016

Co-Founder & CEO – G.A.P Institute

3 successful startups with series-A fundraise

Former Director of Marketing & Admissions

at VinUniversity, Vingroup

10+ years experience in consulting,

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The word "Agenda" is written in a large, white, sans-serif font, centered within a dark grey rectangular box. The background of the slide is a photograph of several hands of different skin tones being stacked together in a supportive gesture.

1. Lead Trainer Introduction
2. Session Expectation
3. Understanding of the Social-Impact Landscape
4. The initial story – Watch the video clip
5. Design Thinking (Human-Centric Approach)
 1. From India (Stanford Reading)
 2. From Indonesia (Research YCAB)
6. Framework: Impact Model Canvas & Empathy

I.Intro

Forbes
UNDER 30
SUMMIT

EMPOWER THE YOUNG
TP. HỒ CHÍ MINH

“ Đối với tôi, con người không cần phải làm những điều phi thường, họ chỉ cần làm những điều bình thường một cách xuất sắc nhất và đó đã là cách đóng góp tốt nhất cho xã hội ”

LÊ ĐÌNH HIẾU
Trưởng nhóm Global Shapers TP. HCM

Forbes Vietnam ▶ Forbes Vietnam -
Under 30 Summit 2016

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LÊ ĐÌNH HIẾU, TRƯỞNG NHÓM GLOBAL SHAPERS TP.HCM (WEF Global Shapers Ho Chi Minh City Hub)

Anh Hieu Dinh Le được đánh giá là một người trẻ năng nổ, đóng góp cho hoạt động cộng đồng thông qua con đường giáo dục. Năm 2012, Hiếu đã từ bỏ công việc tại Deloitte để toàn tâm toàn ý cho dự án giáo dục tại Everest Education (E2) mà cậu là một trong bốn sáng lập. Tại E2 – trung tâm đào tạo ngoài giờ giúp h... [See More](#) — with Hieu Dinh Le.

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1 Comment

I.Intro

Exclusive: Vietnam-based Everest Education raises \$1m early stage funding

UNESCO-CEP RA MẮT CHƯƠNG TRÌNH
TODAY'S VOICE - G.A.P INSTITUTE

G.A.P
INSTITUTE

"Chúng tôi xây dựng một lớp trẻ tinh hoa, giàu hoài bão để ghi dấu ấn của người Việt trên cộng đồng quốc tế, và qua đó, tạo tiền đề phát triển và nhân rộng cho các thế hệ tiếp theo."

II. Expectation

1. Understand the “impact enterprise” model
2. Understand successful case studies
3. Understand of the Social-Impact landscape in Vietnam
4. Develop ideas for your own firm
5. Be able to use the Impact Model Canvas

III. Landscape

The business model spectrum revisited

III. Landscape

IV. The Story

A photograph showing the silhouettes of people walking on a street at night. They are carrying baskets or containers on their heads and shoulders. The scene is illuminated by warm, yellow streetlights, creating a bokeh effect in the background. The overall mood is one of quiet activity and daily life.

every social initiative starts with a story

V. Design Thinking

V. Design Thinking

V. Design Thinking *Lesson from India*

V. Design Thinking *Lesson from India*

**The
Guardian**

V. Design Thinking

1. Break things up
2. Look for scale independent patterns
3. Articulate local behaviors
4. Amplify what's working

V. Design Thinking

What is Human Centered Design

- the needs of people
- the possibilities of technology
- the requirements for success

THE ANSWER

VI. FRAMEWORK

SUSTAINABLE CANVAS

VI. FRAMEWORK

PRACTICE

Work in your team or on your own in 20 mins and complete the Sustainable Model Canvas for your business ideas.

<https://forms.gle/pfC3zCagjHM13qHH6>

Key Partners Who are our Key Partners? Who are our key suppliers? Which Key Resources are we acquiring from partners? Which Key Activities do partners perform? MOTIVATION FOR PARTNERSHIPS: Optimization and economy Reduction of risk and uncertainty Acquisition of particular resources and activities	Key Activities What Key Activities do our Value Propositions require? Our Distribution Channels? Customer Relationships? Revenue Streams? CATEGORIES: Production Problem Solving Platform/Network	Value Propositions What value do we deliver to the customer? Which one of our customer's problems are we helping to solve? What bundles of products and services are we offering to each Customer Segment? Which customer needs are we satisfying? CHARACTERISTICS: Newness Performance Customization „Getting the Job Done“ Design Brand Status Price Cost Reduction Risk Reduction Accessibility Convenience/Usability	Customer Relationships What type of relationship does each of our Customer Segments expect us to establish and maintain with them? Which ones have we established? How are they integrated with the rest of our business model? How costly are they? EXAMPLES: Personal Assistance Dedicated Personal Assistance Self Service Automated Services Communities Co-Creation	Customer Segments For whom are we creating value? Who are our most important customers? POSSIBILITIES: Mass Market Niche Market Segmented Diversified Multi-sided Platform
Key Resources What Key Resources do our Value Propositions require? Our Distribution Channels? Customer Relationships? Revenue Streams? TYPES OF RESOURCES: Physical Intellectual (brand patents, copyrights, data) Human Financial	Channels Through which Channels do our Customer Segments want to be reached? How are we reaching them now? How are our Channels integrated? Which ones work best? Which ones are most cost-efficient? How are we integrating them with customer routines? CHANNEL PHASES: 1. Awareness 2. Evaluation 3. Purchase 4. Delivery 5. After Sales (post-purchase customer support) ...of products & services and Value Proposition	Cost Structure What are the most important costs inherent in our business model? Which Key Resources are the most expensive? Which Key Activities are most expensive? IS YOUR BUSINESS MORE: Cost Driven (lowest cost structure, low price value proposition, maximum automation, extensive outsourcing) Value Driven (focused on value creation, premium value proposition) SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: Fixed Costs (salaries, rents, utilities) Variable Costs Economies of Scale Economies of Scope	Revenue Streams For what value are our customers really willing to pay? For what do they currently pay? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues? FIXED PRICING: List Price Product feature dependent Customer segment dependent Volume dependent DYNAMIC PRICING: Negotiation (bargaining) Yield management Real-time Market TYPES: Asset Sale Subscription Fees Usage Fee Lending/Renting/Leasing Licensing Brokerage Fees	
Eco-Social Costs What ecological or social costs is our business model causing? Which Key Resources are non-renewable? Which Key Activities use a lot of resources? EVALUATION INSTRUMENTS: Life-Cycle Assessment (of products and services) Common Good Balance Sheet	Eco-Social Benefits What ecological or social benefits is our business model generating? Who are the beneficiaries? Are they potential customers? Can we transform the benefits into a Value Proposition? If yes, for whom? INSTRUMENTS: Social Reporting Standard Common Good Balance Sheet			

VI. FRAMEWORK

EMPATHIZE WITH THE BENEFICIARIES

say

think

do

feel

WHAT IS EMPATHY?

YOU CAN THINK THROUGH THE
EXPERIENCE OF ANOTHER BY
UNDERSTANDING IT COMPLETELY

WHY IS EMPATHY IMPORTANT?

YOU WANT TO
DESIGN SOMETHING
THAT WILL BE USED
BY PEOPLE

TO DESIGN SOMETHING
THAT PEOPLE WILL USE, IT
HAS TO FILL A NEED AND
FIT INTO THEIR LIVES IN A
MEANINGFUL WAY

TO DESIGN SOMETHING
MEANINGFUL YOU NEED
TO UNDERSTAND THEIR
LIVES, THEIR BEHAVIOR,
THEIR BELIEFS

NEED FINDING

DISCOVERING PEOPLE'S EXPLICIT AND IMPLICIT NEEDS SO THAT YOU CAN MEET THEM THROUGH YOUR DESIGNS

NEED

A PHYSICAL, PSYCHOLOGICAL OR CULTURAL REQUIREMENT OF AN INDIVIDUAL OR GROUP THAT IS MISSING OR NOT MET THROUGH EXISTING SOLUTIONS

NEEDFINDING

An iceberg floating in the ocean. The tip of the iceberg is above the water line, and the much larger, submerged part is below. The sky is blue with light clouds, and the water is a deep blue. The iceberg is white and jagged.

EXPLICIT

IMPLICIT

MEANING

V. Design Thinking

Lesson from Indonesia

Child by child
We build our Nation

- YCAB, established in Indonesia in **1999**, started with **six staff** members and five advisers. Now YCAB has evolved into a group of social enterprise with more than **655 paid staff** and **3000 supporters**.
- Program-wise, YCAB has also grown exponentially²². From reaching out to around 2000 youths in 1999, now it has spread its wings to serve more than **2.7 million** at the bottom of the pyramid at **5 other countries**: Afghanistan, Mongolia, Myanmar, Pakistan and Uganda.
- By the end of 2020, YCAB aims to touch the lives of a **five million people**.

A photograph of several hands of different skin tones stacked on top of each other, symbolizing unity and support. The hands are positioned on the left side of the frame, with the fingers pointing towards the center.

YOUR OWN BENEFICIARIES